

DAMAGE AND FAILURE MODELLING OF FIBRE-POLYMER COMPOSITES IN FIRE

A.P. Mouritz, S. Feih, E. Kandare
School of Aerospace, Mechanical & Manufacturing Engineering, RMIT University,
GPO Box 2476V, Melbourne, Victoria, Australia, 3001.
adrian.mouritz@rmit.edu.au, s.feih@rmit.edu.au & e.kandare@rmit.edu.au

Z. Mathys
Defence Science & Technology Organisation, GPO Box 4331, Melbourne, Victoria,
Australia, 3001.
zenka.mathys@dsto.defence.gov.au

A.G. Gibson
Centre for Composite Materials Engineering, University of Newcastle-upon-Tyne,
Newcastle, England, NE1 7RU.
a.g.gibson@ncl.ac.uk

P. Des Jardin
Department of Mechanical & Aerospace Engineering, University of Buffalo,
The State University of New York, Buffalo, NY, USA, 14260-4400.
ped@eng.buffalo.edu

S. Case
Department of Engineering Science & Mechanics, Virginia Polytechnic Institute &
State University, Blacksburg, VA, USA, 24061.
scase@exchange.vt.edu

B. Lattimer
Department of Mechanical Engineering, Virginia Polytechnic Institute & State
University, Blacksburg, VA, USA, 24061.
lattimer@vt.edu

SUMMARY

This keynote paper presents a critical review of research progress in modelling the damage and failure of polymer matrix composites exposed to fire. Models for analysing the thermal, chemical and physical processes that control the structural response and failure of composite materials in fire are briefly reviewed.

Keywords: polymer matrix composites, fire, damage, mechanical properties

INTRODUCTION

This paper presents a critical review of progress in the analysis of damage and failure of fibre-polymer composite materials in fire. Fire performance is one of the most significant factors affecting the wider use of composites in engineering structures. The types of composites used in engineering structures decompose when exposed to high temperature fire (typically above several hundred degrees) with the release of heat, smoke and combustion gases. The fire reaction properties of structural composite materials have been characterized, and information is available on their time-to-ignition, heat release rate, limiting oxygen index, flame spread, smoke density and smoke toxicity production [1].

The progress in the modelling and measurement of the fire reaction properties of composite materials has, until recently, not been matched by advances in analysing their damage, structural behaviour and failure in fire. Understanding the damage and failure in fire is a critical safety issue because the loss in stiffness, strength and creep resistance can cause composite structures to distort and collapse; possibly resulting in injury and death. The structural response of composites in fire is arguably as important to safety as the fire reaction properties that have been more widely studied. Therefore, modelling the fire structural response of composites is essential to assessing their survivability and safety.

This paper presents a short overview of research into the modelling of damage and failure of composites in fire. The research has concentrated on polymer laminates reinforced with non-combustible fibres (e.g. glass). The paper describes models for calculating the decomposition, damage and failure of composites in fire. The paper also identifies the deficiencies in the models that must be resolved.

FIRE STRUCTURAL MODELLING

The key challenge with modelling of composites in fire is the complexity of the thermal, chemical, physical and failure processes which control the structural behaviour (figure 1). The challenge to modelling the damage and failure of composites in fire is the accurate analysis of these many processes. The analysis is further complicated because many of the processes do not occur in isolation from each other. Understanding these processes and how they interact is essential to analysing the behaviour of composites in fire.

The general approach to modelling the structural response and failure of composites in fire is outlined in figure 2. The first stage involves thermal modelling to predict the temperature distribution throughout the composite with increasing exposure time to the fire. This stage may involve modelling the fire itself and then coupling the thermal dynamics of the fire to the composite. The next stage involves modelling the damage to the composite, which is dependent on the calculated temperature distribution. Modelling of fire-induced damage, including pore formation, delamination, matrix cracking, fibre-matrix debonding, matrix pyrolysis, fibre softening and char formation, through the composite is essential in the analysis of the phase changes and physical integrity of the composite. The third major stage is the modelling of the structural properties of the composite, which is based on the analysis of the temperature and damage distributions. The modelling is performed to calculate the non-uniform reduction to the mechanical properties through the composite as it heats-up, decomposes and degrades. The final

stage is the prediction of final failure, which is dependent on the residual structural properties of the composite together with the externally applied load and boundary conditions. The following sections to this paper provide an overview of research progress in each of these stages of modelling.

Figure 1. Schematic of the reaction process in the through-thickness direction of a hot, decomposing polymer composite during fire exposure.

Figure 2. Flow-chart showing the major stages in modelling the structural response of composites in fire.

THERMAL MODELLING

Thermal modelling involves calculating the temperature distribution through the composite when subjected to one-sided heating by fire. Accurate modelling of heat transfer through the composite is the critical first stage in fire structural analysis. The thermal analysis of composites in fire is complicated because the heat transfer is controlled by a multitude of temperature-dependent processes which are summarised in

Table 1. Thermal models to calculate the temperature in composites exposed to fire have been developed by Henderson et al. [2], Sullivan and Salamon [3], McManus and Springer [4], Dimitrienko [5], and Gibson et al. [6]. The models all have the capability to calculate the temperature distribution through a composite exposed to fire, but differ in the processes that are considered in the analysis. The processes included in the various thermal models are indicated in Table 1.

Table 1: Summary of the main processes when a composite is exposed to fire. The processes considered in the various thermal models is given. The symbols mean that the model considers (✓) or does not (✗) consider the process. The numbers are the references to the thermal models.

Fire Processes	[2]	[3]	[4]	[5]	[6]
Heat conduction through virgin material and char	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Decomposition of polymer matrix and organic fibres	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Flow of gases from the reaction zone through the char zone	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Thermal expansion/contraction	✗	✓	✓	✓	✗
Pressure rise	✗	✓	✓	✓	✗
Formation of delamination, matrix cracks & voids	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗
Reactions between char and fibre reinforcement	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗
Ablation	✗	✗	✓	✗	✗

Thermal model most often used to calculate the temperature in composites exposed to fire were developed by Henderson et al. [2]:

$$\rho C_p \frac{\partial T}{\partial t} = k_{\perp} \frac{\partial^2 T}{\partial x^2} + \frac{\partial k_{\perp}}{\partial x} \frac{\partial T}{\partial x} - \dot{m}_g C_{p(g)} \frac{\partial T}{\partial x} - \frac{\partial p}{\partial t} (Q_p + h_c - h_g) \quad [1]$$

where T is temperature; x is distance below the heated surface; ρ and C_p is density and specific heat capacity of the composite; k_{\perp} is through-thickness thermal conductivity; \dot{m}_g and $C_{p(g)}$ is mass flux and specific heat of decomposition gases, respectively; Q_p is decomposition energy of polymer matrix; and h_c and h_g are the enthalpies of the composite and decomposition gases, respectively. This equation analyses one-dimensional heat transfer in the through-thickness direction of the composite, but it can be expanded to analyse two- and three-dimensional heat flow. It can also be amended to analyse heat transfer in sandwich materials. By iteratively solving the equation for increasing temperature and time ($\delta T / \delta t$) at the heated surface it is possible to calculate the temperature at any location in the composite.

The solution of the models requires a large amount of empirical data on the thermal and decomposition properties of the composite. Thermal property data (k_{\perp} , C_p) and decomposition reaction rate constants must be measured over a large temperature range, which may be many hundreds of degrees. Other properties must be assumed or estimated because it is difficult to accurately measure the value. Validation of the model by experimental fire testing has shown they can usually predict the temperature at any location in laminate (as shown for example in figure 3) and sandwich composite materials with good accuracy.

In summary, thermal models [2-6] have been developed to calculate the temperature in laminates and sandwich composites exposed to fire. These models can predict with good accuracy the temperature rise in composites containing non-reactive fibres (e.g. fibreglass). However, the capability of thermal models to analyse the temperature of composites containing reactive fibres (e.g. carbon, Kevlar), where oxidation and decomposition of the fibres influence the temperature, has not been adequately addressed. Furthermore, thermal models do not consider the influence of fire-induced damage, such as delamination cracking and skin-core debonding, on the heat flow process. Critical to modelling this is predicting internal pressures produced by pyrolysis gases and the flow of these gases within the material. Research needs to be performed to expand the understanding of this behaviour. The effects of radiation transmission into the material should also be included in these models. New thermal models are currently being developed which consider fire-induced damage; however their accuracy has not been established against experimental temperature data.

Figure 3. Comparison of the theoretical (solid curves) and measured (data point) temperature profiles in a woven glass-vinyl ester laminate when exposed to simulated fire conditions involving one-sided heating at the heat flux of 50 kW/m^2 . Temperatures measured at the front face (fire exposed), centre and back face of the laminate.

FIRE DAMAGE MODELLING

Damage caused to laminates and sandwich composites in fire has been a topic of intensive investigation in recent years because of the influence on structural properties. The fire-induced damage experienced by laminates includes matrix decomposition, pore formation, delamination cracking, matrix cracking, fibre-matrix debonding, and char formation. Fire-induced damage to composite structures is difficult to accurately model because it is dependent on many parameters, with the main factors being the temperature and duration of the fire; the volumetric dilations and toughness properties of the material at high temperature, and the type and magnitude of external loading (including the boundary conditions). Some progress has been achieved in modelling the initiation and growth of voids, delaminations and char in polymer laminates [5,7-9].

However, the models currently consider only one type of damage, and a unified modelling approach that analyses concurrently the initiation and development of the many types of damage has not been developed.

Gas-filled pores develop in the polymer matrix and at the fibre-matrix interface during decomposition of composite materials in fire. The pores initiate, grow and coalesce in the hot, viscous matrix under the high internal pressures exerted by decomposition gases. Sullivan and Salamon [4] developed a model based on the conservation of gas mass principle to calculate the diffusion of gases through a hot, decomposing composite. Dimitrienko et al. [5] formulated an analytical expression that relates the mass loss of the polymer matrix due to decomposition to the gas pressure in the pores:

$$\frac{\partial m}{\partial t} = A \left[1 - \frac{p}{p_o} e^{-(2E/RT)} \right]^{1/2} e^{-E/RT} \quad [2]$$

where m is mass; A and E is the pre-exponential reaction constant and activation energy for matrix decomposition, respectively, p and p_o is internal and ambient pressure of the composite, respectively; and R is universal gas constant. The local pressure is estimated as high as 15 times above the ambient pressure, which is high enough to cause delamination damage, matrix cracking and fibre-matrix debonding as well as pores. Therefore, analysis of the internal pressure rise is important for modelling the formation of damage in composites exposed to fire.

Delamination cracking occurs in laminates and sandwich materials exposed to fire, and this damage can severely weaken composite structures supporting compression or in-plane shear loads. The cracking is due to the internal pressure rise, thermally-induced strains caused by thermal expansion, and reduced interlaminar fracture toughness caused by matrix softening. Several models have been developed to predict the fire-induced strains due to thermal expansion. For example, Florio et al. [7] developed a model to predict the axial expansion of a decomposing composite exposed to fire. The strain is approximated using:

$$\frac{\partial \epsilon(T)}{\partial t} = \alpha_v F \frac{\partial T}{\partial t} + \alpha_c (1-F) \frac{\partial T}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \left(\eta T + \xi \frac{m}{m_o} \right) \quad [3]$$

where α_v and α_c are the thermal expansion coefficients of the virgin and decomposed phases of the composite, respectively; F is the mass fraction of virgin material in the decomposing composite; m and m_o are the instantaneous and original mass of polymer matrix; and η and ξ are empirical constants.

The progress in modelling the thermal strains and resultant delamination cracking has not been matched by experimental research into the interlaminar fracture toughness properties of composites at high temperature. Analysis of delamination cracking requires experimental data on the interlaminar fracture toughness properties between the ambient and matrix decomposition temperatures (typically 300-400°C). Published data on the elevated temperature interlaminar toughness properties of composites is mostly below 200°C, and higher temperature data up to decomposition is lacking.

Modelling decomposition of the polymer matrix into volatile gases and char is important for analysing the phase changes and structural behaviour of composites in fire. The mass loss of a polymer that decomposes via a single-stage reaction process is calculated using the Arrhenius kinetic rate equation:

$$\frac{\partial m}{\partial t} = -Am_o \left(\frac{m - m_f}{m_o} \right)^n e^{(-E/RT)} \quad [4]$$

Modelling char formation is also important in analysing the decomposition and structural response of composites in fire. Gibson et al. [10] have shown that equation 4 can be used to analyse the formation and growth of the char phase in laminates exposed to fire. It was observed that visible char formation in thermoset laminates starts when the mass fraction of the polymer matrix is reduced by ~20% due to decomposition and vapourisation. Using this as the criteria for char formation, the extent of char growth in laminates can be calculated based on the mass loss. Figure 4 compares the theoretical and measured thickness of the char zone in thermoset laminates when exposed to one-sided heating under simulated fire conditions. The char thickness (d_c) is normalised to the total laminate thickness (d). With the exception of a few outliers there is good agreement between the calculated (based on 20% mass loss) and the measured values for char thickness. This progress in modelling the decomposition of the polymer matrix into char for laminates has not been matched by modelling for sandwich composites, where a validated char model is lacking.

In summary, there has been good progress in the development and validation of models to predict matrix decomposition and char formation in laminates. There has also been some progress in modelling the formation and growth of delaminations and gas-filled pores. However, most of the models restrict the analysis to a single type of damage, and the challenge is the development of a unified damage model that analyses concurrently all types of damage including fibre-matrix debonding, intraply matrix cracking and fibre damage.

Figure 4. Comparison of the calculated and measured thickness of the char zone in laminate materials exposed to simulated fire conditions of different heat flux values. The char thickness values (d_c) are normalised to the laminate thickness (d).

STRUCTURAL & FAILURE MODELLING OF COMPOSITES IN FIRE

There has been major progress in recent years in the development of models to analyse the mechanical properties and failure of composites under combined compression loading and one-sided heating by fire. The models analyse a composite panel that is loaded axially at a constant compression load while simultaneously being heated from one side by fire. The models use different mechanical theories to analyse the reduction to the compression properties as the material is heated by fire. The mechanical analysis includes average strength [11-13], Euler buckling [14] and visco-elastic softening [15] for laminates and skin failure [16], buckling [14,17] and skin wrinkling [18] models for sandwich composites. The models also differ in the scale of the analysis, ranging from unit cell analysis of the individual fibres and polymer matrix to ply-by-ply analysis to bulk analysis in which the ply properties are smeared over the volume of material. The models are solved analytically or using finite element methods. The capability of one type of model (based on average strength) to predict the failure times of a fiberglass laminate under compression loading while being heated from one-side at different heat flux values is shown in figure 5. The theoretical predictions of the failure times (shown by the solid curves) show reasonable agreement with the measured times (data points), except at low stress and heat flux conditions when creep effects are dominant, and this is an area where model improvement is required by time-dependent analysis.

Figure 5. Comparison of compression failure times calculated using the average strength model by Feih et al. [12] and measured experimentally for a woven glass-vinyl ester laminate.

Modelling the fire structural response of composites under tension loading is more complicated than compression because softening and failure of both the polymer matrix and fibre reinforcement must be analysed. Less research has been performed into the fire tension properties of composites than their compression properties. Feih et al. [19] recently developed a modelling approach to analyse softening and failure of fibreglass laminates under combined tension and one-sided heating by fire. The model can predict the failure times of fibreglass laminates under tension loading, as shown in figure 6.

However, like the compression failure models, the tension model by Feih et al. [19] does not analyse all the damage processes which control the mechanical properties and failure. The effects of thermal strain, pore formation, delamination, fibre-matrix debonding, and viscoplastic creep effects are not considered, and the development of new models that consider these processes in determining the tensile structure response is required. A model to analyse the tensile response of sandwich composites exposed to fire is also required.

Figure 6. Comparison of tensile failure times calculated using the average strength model by Feih et al. [19] and measured experimentally for a woven glass-vinyl ester laminate.

Despite recent progress in the development of thermal-mechanical models for calculating the fire structural response and failure of composites, much remains to be done. There is a need to improve the numerical robustness of existing models in solving highly non-linear behaviour. Models to analyse the fire structural behaviour of composites under other loading conditions (e.g. shear, torsion, fatigue) have not been developed. Lastly, there is a need to develop mechanistic-based models which accurately analyse the mechanisms and processes controlling the temperature distribution, damage, softening and failure. The development of mechanistic models will not only improve the accuracy of the predictions, but will reduce the reliance on large amounts of empirical data. The growing use of composites in high fire risk applications demands the on-going development of fire structural models for laminates and sandwich materials.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors acknowledge funding support from the U.S. Office of Naval Research (Grant Nos. N00014-04-10026, N00014-07-10514, N00014-03-1-0369, N00014-06-1-0623) managed by Dr Luise Couchman. The research work by APM, SF, EK, and ZM

was performed as a part of the Cooperative Research Centre for Advanced Composite Structures (Project 2.1.2).

REFERENCES

1. A.P. Mouritz and A.G. Gibson, *Fire Properties of Polymer Composite Materials*, Springer, Dordrecht, 2006.
2. J.B. Henderson, J.A. Wiebelt and M.R. Tant. A model for the thermal response of polymer composite materials with experimental verification. *Journal of Composite Materials*, 1985;19:579-595.
3. H.L. McManus and G.S. Springer, *Journal of Composite Materials*, **26**, (1992), 230-255.
4. R.M. Sullivan and N.J. Salamon. *International Journal of Engineering Science*, 1992;30:431-441.
5. Y.I. Dimitrienko. *Composites*, 1997;28A:453-461.
6. A.G. Gibson, Y.-S. Wu, H.W. Chandler, J.A.D. Wilcox and P. Bettess. *Revue de L'Institut Francais du Petrole*, 1995;50:69-74.
7. J. Florio, J.B. Henderson, F.L. Test and R. Hariharan. *International Journal of Heat & Mass Transfer*, 1991;34:135-147.
8. C. Luo and P.E. DesJardin, Evaluation of thermal transport properties using a micro-cracking model for woven composite laminates, *Proceedings of the 17th International Conference on Composite Materials*, 27-31 July 2009, Edinburgh, UK.
9. H.L. McManus. Prediction of fire damage to composite aircraft structures. In: *Proceedings of the 9th International Conference on Composite Materials*, Madrid, Spain, July 1993, pp. 929-936.
10. A.G. Gibson, P.H.N. Wright, Y.-S. Wu, A.P. Mouritz, Z. Mathys and C.P. Gardiner, *Plastics, Rubbers & Composites*, 2003; 32,81-90.
11. A.G. Gibson, Y.-S. Wu, J.T. Evans, J.T. and A.P. Mouritz, *Journal of Composite Materials*, **40**, (2006), 639-658.
12. S. Feih, Z. Mathys, A.G. Gibson and A.P. Mouritz, *Composites Science & Technology*, **67**, (2007), 551-564.
13. J. Lua, J. O'Brien, C.T. Key, Y. Wu and B.Y. Lattimer, *Composites*, 37A, (2006), 1024-1039.
14. L. Liu, G.A. Kardomateas, V. Birman, J.W. Holmes and G.J. Simitzes, *Composites*, 37A, (2006), 972-980.
15. J.V. Bausano, J.J. Lesko and S.W. Case, *Composites*, 37A, (2006), 1092-1100.
16. Feih, S., Mathys, Z., Gibson, A.G. and Mouritz, A.P., *Journal of Sandwich Structures & Materials*, **10**, (2008), 217-245.
17. P. Gu and R.J. Asaro, *Composite Structures*, 2009; 88, 461-467.
18. P. Gu and R.J. Asaro, *Fire Safety Journal*, 2008, 43, 151-160.
19. Feih, S., Mouritz, A.P., Mathys, Z. and Gibson, A.G., *Journal of Composite Materials*, **41**, (2007), 2387-2410.